

Boost

Infectious diseases interventions in community-based harm reduction services in Europe

Insights from the BOOST Project multi-modular survey.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Correlation

European Harm Reduction Network

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 Correlation
European Harm Reduction Network

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Creating Possible

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GROEP**

Glossary

C-EHRN	Correlation – European Harm Reduction Network
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
DCR	Drug Consumption Room
DCS	Drug Checking Services
DPNSEE	Drug Policy Network South-East Europe
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EHRA	Eurasian Harm Reduction Association
EMCDDA	European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction
EU/EEA	European Union/European Economic Area
EuroNPUD	European Network of People who Use Drugs
GPs	General practitioners
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HAT	Heroin-assisted Treatment
HBV	Hepatitis B virus
HCV	Hepatitis C virus
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
IDPC	International Drug Policy Consortium
LGBTQI	Lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and queer people
NPS	New Psychoactive Substances
NSP	Needle Syringe Provision
OAT	Opioid Agonist Treatment
PEP	Post-exposure Prophylaxis
PrEP	Pre-exposure Prophylaxis
PLHIV	People living with HIV
PWUD	People who Use Drugs
STI	Sexually Transmitted Infection
THN	Take Home Naloxone
WHO	World Health Organisation

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Introduction

Background and Objectives

People who use drugs and other marginalised groups, such as people experiencing homelessness, sex workers or migrants, are disproportionately affected by the HIV/AIDS and viral hepatitis epidemics. With stigma, discrimination, and criminalisation aggravating health disparities, these communities experience limited access to health services and higher prevalence of infectious diseases compared to the general population.

Among people who inject drugs, the lack of or insufficient access to harm reduction services results in use of contaminated injecting equipment - a major driver of the spread of infectious diseases among this community in Europe. The group is especially disproportionately affected by chronic hepatitis C, with data showing ongoing transmission¹. Furthermore, a significant portion of diagnoses are late diagnoses, which additionally aggravates the course of infections and constitutes a major contributor to further spread of the disease. Currently, every other person currently living with HIV (PLHIV) in the European Union/European Economic Area (EU/EEA) is diagnosed late². Among people contracting HIV through injecting drug use, the proportion of those diagnosed and in treatment is substantially lower than for other PLHIV³ (ECDC & WHO, 2021).

In light of these considerations and recognising the urgent need to address these multiple epidemics to improve the health of affected communities and public health in Europe, the BOOST project aims to strengthen and support community-based and community-led harm reduction organisations⁴ in providing high-quality communicable disease services to people who use drugs. These include the scaling-up of good practices in communicable disease awareness, prevention, screening/testing and linkage to care, delivered as an integrated part of people-centred harm reduction interventions. The landscape of harm reduction in Europe is complex and multifaceted, influenced by varying national and sometimes regional policies, the availability of resources, and the diverse needs of people who use drugs and other groups disproportionately affected by drug and other policies. To respond to these challenges, the BOOST project draws on the collective experiences and strengths of major European harm reduction networks and the European Network of People who Use Drugs (EuroNPUD). The collaboration between major European networks ensures a wide range of experience, and access to different affected populations, covering all EU member states and

1 European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction, *Increasing Access to Hepatitis C Testing and Care for People Who Inject Drugs: Identifying Barriers to and Opportunities for Supporting Hepatitis C Testing and Care in Drug Services: A Participatory Diagnostic Process*. (LU: Publications Office, 2021), <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2810/033126>

2 ECDC, *'ECDC and WHO Call for Improved HIV Testing in Europe'*, 26 November 2020, <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/news-events/ecdc-and-who-call-improved-hiv-testing-europe>.

3 European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, *Continuum of HIV Care: Monitoring Implementation of the Dublin Declaration on Partnership to Fight HIV/AIDS in Europe and Central Asia: 2022 Progress Report*. (LU: Publications Office, 2023), <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2900/721938>

4 Community-based service organisations are those that offer services outside formal healthcare facilities, such as hospitals. When

services are provided by members of the community to which they are targeted, this is described as 'community-led' service provision. Community-led organisations bring together members of key populations and other underserved groups, putting their needs at the centre of the response and ensuring that the voices of the community are heard. The BOOST consortium includes various community-led organisations and in the context of this proposal, the provision of 'community-led' services is to be understood as included in the term 'community-based' services

neighbouring regions. The involvement of and cooperation with affected communities is vital to making health promotion interventions effective and efficient.

BOOST project partners

Correlation – European Harm Reduction Network (Netherlands)

A-Clinic Foundation (Finland)

ABD/Energy Control (Spain)

Drug Policy Network South-East Europe

Eurasian Harm Reduction Association

European Network of People who Use Drugs

Fondazione LILA Milano (Italy)

Free Clinic (Belgium)

IGTP/ICO (Spain)

ISGlobal (Spain)

Re Generation (Serbia)

Spolecnosc Podane Ruce (Czechia)

Villa Maraini Foundation (Italy)

The BOOST project Scientific Expert and Advisory Board (SEAB) supports the development and implementation of work package-specific activities and provides expert and scientific advice. The SEAB includes:

- Alina Bocai – ARAS Foundation (Romania)
- Janelle, Sandberg / Erika Duffel – ECDC (UK)
- Astrid Leicht – Fixpunkt (Germany)
- Mojca Matičič – University Medical Centre, Ljubljana (Slovenia)
- Iciar Indave – EMCDDA (Portugal)
- Tuukka Tammi – THL (Finland)
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- Dagmar Hedrich – Consultant (Germany)
- Eberhard Schatz – Consultant (Netherlands)
- Ferenc Bagyinszky – Deutsche Aidshilfe, AAE (Germany)
- Vana Sypsa – University of Athens (Greece)
- Perrine Roux – INSERM (France)
- Dorte Raben – EuroTEST and European Testing Week Secretariat (Denmark)

The project is based on four areas of activity and delivers results in

- 1 the area of data collection and monitoring among community-based service organisations;
- 2 training and capacity building (including the use of relevant information technology tools towards hard-to-reach populations);
- 3 the boosting of integrated community-based health services (including counselling, peer-support, harm reduction as well as testing and linkage to care) and
- 4 the development of networking and advocacy activities among community-based networks and service organisations.

Activities under Work Package INFORM aim to gather information on current practice and quality of community-based communicable diseases service provision by community-based harm reduction organisations to inform capacity building/learning activities, to identify where implementation support for good practice models is needed; and to design advocacy activities to improve service provision. This Multi-Modular Survey was conducted in summer-autumn 2023 to collect the above-mentioned data, together with information shedding light on the general operation of community-based harm reduction services in the context of infectious diseases services.

Survey Design and Methodology

In response to the ongoing challenges faced by harm reduction organisations across the continent, this comprehensive multi-modular survey was conducted among European community-based harm reduction organisations.

The primary objective of the survey was to gather detailed data on the availability and accessibility of harm reduction and infectious diseases services, the practices, and procedures of monitoring data collection regarding testing for infectious diseases, communication and dissemination practices, digital literacy skills of services' staff, and advocacy priorities of each organisation. A critical aspect of the survey was identifying the barriers and gaps in the provision of essential services, as well as pinpointing areas where capacity-building activities are most needed.

The survey was designed in an iterative consultation process starting in February 2023 during the BOOST project kick-off meeting and continuing for a couple of subsequent months online and in person. The consultations included all project partners and coordinators who provided input regarding their data needs for informing the work of respective Work Packages as well as recommendations and feedback from the members of the BOOST Scientific Advisory Board. The resulting questionnaire included 63 questions divided into six major parts:

- Part I: Organisation details
- Part II: Availability of services
- Part III: Functioning of services and networking
- Part IV: Digital literacy and digital tools
- Part V: Testing data collection and reporting practices
- Part VI: Communication, advocacy and capacity building.

This report focuses on discussing (in full or in part) questions included in Parts I-III and VI as the information gathered in the remaining parts was intended for the internal use of the project.

The data collection took place from June to October 2023 using Survey Monkey. The survey was disseminated among more than 200 members of the three major networks involved in the BOOST project: Correlation - European Harm Reduction Network (C-EHRN), Eurasian Harm Reduction Association (EHRA), and the European Network of People who Use Drugs (EuroNPUD), as well as the Drug Policy Network South-East Europe

(DPNSEE). The questions primarily asked for information about respondents' service-providing organisations, with a few exceptions where the survey asked about the situation in the respondents' respective countries.

Participation and Response Rate

The survey was disseminated electronically to the designated contact persons at each of the over 200 member organisations. Participation was encouraged through a series of follow-up communications and extensions of the data collection deadline. The response rate was relatively high, with 82 responses collected (including 64 complete and eligible responses), reflecting a high level of engagement and a recognition of the survey's importance among the harm reduction community.

Geographically, the respondents are spread across a wide range of European countries, including but not limited to Poland, Germany, Greece, Spain, and France, as well as countries from the broader Eurasian region such as Georgia and Kyrgyzstan (see the map 1 below for the number of responses per country⁵).

⁵ In addition to the countries shown on the map, following number of responses was collected from: Azerbaijan – 1; Georgia – 3; Kazakhstan – 1; Kyrgyzstan – 1.

The number of responses per country

Map 1. The number of responses per country

The respondent pool for the survey comprises an expert group of professionals from a broad spectrum of roles within harm reduction organisations across Europe and Eurasia. With a total of 64 respondents representing 29 different countries, the diversity in both geographical and professional terms enhance the reliability and relevance of the data collected. The roles of these respondents include high-level positions such as executive directors, and various types of managers, as well as more specialised positions like medical directors and harm reduction officers. This variety ensures that the survey captures a wide range of perspectives and insights into the operational, strategic, and clinical aspects of examined harm reduction services. The geographical spread, encompassing countries from Western, Central, and Eastern Europe, as well as the Eurasian region, further ensures that the survey reflects a wide array of regulatory environments, cultural contexts, and public health challenges. Therefore, the respondent pool is not only appropriate but also highly informed and equipped with the necessary expertise to provide reliable information on the availability, barriers, and needs related to STI, HIV, and viral hepatitis services in their respective regions.

Data Processing and Analysis

Out of 82 initial responses, 64 were complete and eligible. Incomplete and ineligible responses (e.g., falling outside of the geographical scope of the study) as well as possible duplicate responses were removed.

Data analysis was conducted using statistical tools of Microsoft Excel and SPSS to produce descriptive statistics.

Basic characteristics of community-based harm reduction services

Primary and secondary areas of focus/activities

In the first part of the survey, the respondents were asked about the primary and secondary areas of activity or focus of their organisation.

Most responses (42.2%, 27 responses) identify 'community-led services' as the primary area of activity, confirming that the surveyed organisations are significantly involved in initiatives that are driven by the community of people who use drugs. Further, 'social services' received a notable portion of responses (23.4%, 15 responses), followed by 'health services' (18.8%, 12 responses).

Other areas such as 'advocacy', and 'networking' were identified as the primary area of activity by very few respondents, garnering around 4.7% (three responses each); 'training' was mentioned by two respondents (3.1%). No responses were recorded for 'research' and 'legislation and policy', indicating that these are not primary areas of focus of the respondent organisations.

Overall, the data suggests that surveyed services are primarily community-driven, with significant involvement in social and health services. This aligns with the general characteristics of community-led organisations, which are typically deeply integrated into the communities they serve, focusing on local needs and leveraging community strengths.

Figure 1. The primary and secondary areas of activity of the surveyed community-based harm reduction organisations (N=64, skipped: 0).

Primary and secondary areas or activities

Considering the secondary area of activity, the highest percentage of responses is for ‘social services’, which accounts for 29.7% (19 responses), followed closely by ‘health services’, with 26.6% (17 responses).

‘Community-led services’ and ‘advocacy’ each garnered 14.1% of the responses (9 responses each).

Interestingly, ‘research’ and ‘legislation and policy’ received some attention as the secondary focus area, with 6.3% (4 responses) and 4.7% (3 responses) respectively. No responses were recorded for ‘training’ and ‘networking’.

Table 1 below provides a detailed matrix that outlines the primary and secondary focus areas or activities of the surveyed organisations, showing how these organisations allocate their efforts across multiple domains, hence reflecting their operational and strategic priorities. The numbers within the matrix indicate the count of organisations that have reported a particular area as a secondary focus in relation to their primary focus.

Table 1. The matrix outlining the primary and secondary focus areas or activities of the surveyed organisations.

Focus area of activity combinations

Main focus \ Secondary focus	Health	Social	Community-led	Research	Legislation and policy	Advocacy	Other	Total
Health	0	10	0	0	0	2	0	12
Social	7	0	3	0	1	2	2	15
Community-led	9	7	2	3	1	4	1	27
Advocacy	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	3
Training	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	2
Networking	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	3
Other	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2
Total	17	19	9	4	3	9	3	64

- health services and social services
- health services and community-led services
- social services and community-led services
- advocacy and community-led service

The table shows that several dominant focus area combinations appear among the examined harm reduction services.

A significant observation from the matrix is the prevalence of organisations that maintain a narrow focus, reporting ‘health’ and ‘social services’ as the main areas of activity. This is the most prevalent combination (a total of 17 organisations, 26.6%), where most organisations providing primarily health services have social services as their secondary focus, and the other way around. This suggests a concentrated effort or specialisation in these two areas, which is likely due to the critical nature of health and social services in addressing comprehensive community needs in the context of harm reduction and communicable diseases.

On the other hand, the presence of numbers across different focus areas for

each primary category indicates a more cross-functional approach where organisations are not limiting their activities to a single domain but are instead integrating multiple service areas.

For example, organisations with a primary focus on community-led services show a diverse spread regarding the secondary focus across almost all categories, with the most prevalent combinations being with social services (10 organisations, 15.6%), health services (9 organisations, 14.1%), and advocacy (6 organisations, 9.4%). This diversity highlights their role in bridging various community needs from health to advocacy and networking and could be attributed to the grassroots nature of these services, which necessitates a broader engagement with community issues. A relatively high proportion of community-led organisations engaging in advocacy as a secondary focus underscores the importance of activities aiming to influence policy or garner support for community-specific issues.

Moreover, the matrix reveals interesting insights into less common but critical areas such as research, and legislation and policy, which have fewer organisations reporting them as a primary focus but appear as secondary focuses in conjunction with other services. This suggests that while some organisations primarily engage in direct service delivery, they also recognise the importance of supporting research and policymaking to underpin their work with evidence and favourable legal frameworks.

The data also highlights the interconnectedness of various service areas, suggesting that tackling complex social issues often requires a multifaceted approach that leverages different types of expertise and interventions. For instance, the overlap between 'social services' and 'community-led services' in ten organisations points to a collaborative approach in addressing social issues at the community level, combining professional social work with community-driven initiatives.

The above data not only map out the primary and secondary focuses of the surveyed organisations but also paints a picture of the collaborative and interconnected nature of social, health, and community services. It underscores the complexity of community and social issues that require organisations to operate across multiple domains to effectively address the needs of people who use drugs.

The number of clients and client contacts

The data provided in the questions about the number of clients and client contacts reflects the monitoring and reporting practices of the surveyed organisations in relation to their service delivery in 2022. Due to significant differences between the forms of answers to these questions, it is not possible to assess the data in a way that allows for discussing the concrete numbers. However, this diversity of answers shows the extent to which the

surveyed organisations track and record interactions with individuals and the frequency of service delivery. More specifically: 33 respondents reported having complete data on both the number of individual visitors or service participants and the number of client contacts (occasions of service delivery), indicating a robust data collection system in nearly half of the surveyed entities. 17 respondents had data available only for one of these metrics, either the number of individuals or the number of client contacts, and indicated a lack of data for the other metric, suggesting a partial approach to data tracking which might be due to various operational or resource constraints. 9 respondents provided identical numbers in both questions, suggesting that only one of these metrics is being monitored, not clear which. 5 respondents did not have any data on either metric, highlighting a significant gap in their ability to monitor and evaluate service delivery effectively. This indicates that while a significant portion of respondents were able to provide complete data on both individual clients and client contacts, there were still many organisations that either did not collect this data or had limitations in their data collection methods. The incomplete data from some respondents highlights the challenges organisations may face in accurately capturing and reporting on the full scope of their service delivery, particularly for activities like outreach that may not be as easily tracked. This is corroborated by several responses including only data on specific programmes, such as opioid agonist treatment (OAT) or Naloxone distribution programmes, and lack of data for entire organisations. Anonymity and confidentiality policies in services are also mentioned as the reason for not collecting specific types of data.

Network membership

The respondents were also asked about the membership of their organisations in the four networks collaborating on the BOOST project. Figure 2 below represents the distribution of the networks' membership.

Figure 2. Network membership of the survey respondents (N=64, skipped: 0)

Network membership

The survey organisations are most frequently members of Correlation – European Harm Reduction Network (C-EHRN), with 73.4% of respondents (47 out of 64) indicating membership. This suggests a strong alignment and interest in the initiatives and goals pursued by C-EHRN. The Eurasian Harm Reduction Association (EHRA) is the next most common affiliation, with 35.9% (23 out of 64) of the members involved. Membership in the European Network of People who Use Drugs (EuroNPUD) and the Drug Policy Network South-East Europe (DPNSEE) is less common, reported by 23.4% (15 out of 64) and 20.3% (13 out of 64) of respondents, respectively. Additionally, a notable 39.1% (25 out of 64) of respondents are affiliated with other networks not listed in the provided options (for example, IDPC, AIDS Action Europe), highlighting a diverse range of engagements in various initiatives or networks beyond the ones specified.

More specifically, out of 64 organisations:

- Nine are not members of any of the four networks;
- 29 are members of one of the networks, including:
 - 25 C-EHRN members
 - 2 EHRA members
 - 2 EuroNPUD members
- 14 are members of two networks, including:
 - 6 members of C-EHRN & EHRA
 - 3 members of C-EHRN & EuroNPUD
 - 1 member of C-EHRN & DPNSEE
 - 3 members of EHRA & EuroNPUD
 - 1 member of EHRA & DPNSEE
- 7 are members of three networks, including:
 - 5 members of C-EHRN, EHRA and DPNSEE
 - 1 member of C-EHRN, EuroNPUD and DPNSEE
 - 1 member of C-EHRN, EHRA and EuroNPUD
- 5 are members of all 4 networks.

Advocacy and policy engagement

Involvement in policy making

To complement the information regarding the focus of the surveyed organisations' activity, they were also asked about their engagement in policy making and advocacy. Figure 3 presents data on the extent to which organisations engage as civil society actors in policy making processes across different levels: local/regional, national, European, and international. The data is structured to reflect the degree of engagement, ranging from 'To a great extent' to 'Not at all'. This structured approach provides a nuanced view of how harm reduction service provider civil society organisations participate in the policymaking processes, revealing both the intensity and scope of their involvement.

Level of engagement in policy making

- to a great extent
- to a moderate extent
- to a some extent
- to a small extent
- not at all

Figure 3. The extent to which surveyed organisations engage in policy making processes (N=64, skipped: 0).

At the local or regional level, the data shows a significant engagement, with 54.7% of respondents indicating that their organisation engages 'to a great extent.' This high percentage suggests that CSOs are most active and influential at levels closer to their immediate operational environments, where they likely feel they have a more direct impact and where local issues might be more aligned with their specific missions. The extent of involvement progressively decreases as the engagement level lessens, with only 4.7% of respondents indicating no engagement at all. This trend underscores the critical role that CSOs play in shaping local and regional policies, possibly due to greater accessibility to local government structures and a stronger connection with local communities.

At the national level, the engagement is slightly less pronounced but still substantial, with 37.5% of organisations engaging 'to a great extent.' The

engagement levels show a more evenly distributed pattern across the involvement levels compared to the local/regional level. This distribution might reflect the complexities and challenges of influencing national policies, which require navigating more complex bureaucratic structures and a broader range of issues that may not align as directly with the specific objectives of individual organisations.

The overall engagement drops significantly at the European level, with only 7.8% of respondents indicating engagement 'to a great extent.' Most responses shift towards 'to some extent' and 'to a small extent,' with 26.6% and 32.8% respectively. This shift could be attributed to the challenges posed by engaging with supranational bodies like the European Union, where policymaking processes are more complex and distant from direct citizen influence. The higher percentage of respondents indicating no engagement at all (14.1%) at this level could reflect a perceived lack of efficacy or the daunting nature of engaging at such a high level.

At the international level, engagement is the lowest, with only 3.1% of organisations engaging 'to a great extent' and a significant 25% not engaging at all. This minimal engagement could be due to the global scope of issues and the logistical, financial and capacity, and strategic challenges associated with influencing international policies. The international arena may also be saturated with numerous actors, including states and large international NGOs, making it difficult for smaller organisations to find their place.

Involvement in advocacy

Figure 4 presents the data on the extent to which the surveyed harm reduction services engage in advocacy activities across different levels: local/regional, national, European, and international.

Similar to policy making, at the local or regional level, a significant majority of surveyed organisations (56.3%) report engaging in advocacy 'to a great extent'. This high percentage underscores the importance of local and regional advocacy as an essential activity for organisations. The familiarity with local contexts, proximity to the issues at hand, and possibly stronger networks within local communities could explain this preference. Moreover, the relatively lower percentages of engagement at higher levels might reflect the increasing complexity and resource requirements associated with national or international advocacy.

Level of engagement in advocacy activities

Figure 4. The extent to which surveyed organisations engage in advocacy activities (N=64, skipped: 0).

The data also reveals a notable drop in engagement ‘to a great extent’ at the national level (39.1%), which further declines at the European (9.4%) and international levels (4.7%). This trend highlights several critical aspects of advocacy work. First, it points to the challenges organisations face as they attempt to scale their advocacy efforts beyond local contexts. These challenges could range from limited resources and expertise to navigate broader political landscapes, to the difficulty of building and maintaining effective coalitions across diverse stakeholders. The significant drop at the European and international levels, in particular, suggests that barriers to entry are highest in these arenas, possibly due to the complexity of issues, the multiplicity of actors involved, and the need for highly specialised knowledge to engage effectively.

Moreover, the data on engagement ‘to a small extent’ and ‘not at all’ inversely mirrors the trend observed for high engagement, with the percentages increasing as we move from local (4.7% and 1.5%, respectively) to international levels (32.8% and 26.6%, respectively). This inversion further underscores the difficulties organisations encounter as they try to influence policy and practice on a larger scale. It could also reflect a strategic decision by organisations to focus their limited resources where they believe they can make the most difference, which, according to the data, appears to be at the local or regional level.

Interestingly, the percentage of organisations that engage ‘to some extent’ remains relatively stable across all levels, hovering around 10–23%. This consistency might indicate a baseline level of engagement that organisations maintain across different advocacy arenas, possibly to keep up with developments, build networks, or lay the groundwork for future, more intensive engagement.

Provision of Services: Harm reduction

The major part of the multi-modular survey focused on mapping a range of services available in or via community-based and community-led harm reduction organisations in Europe. The list of relevant services was selected based on the WHO Consolidated guidelines on HIV, viral hepatitis and STI prevention, diagnosis, treatment and care for key populations. The following sections discuss the landscape of services provided by these organisations in more detail.

Figure 5. The provision of selected harm reduction services by the surveyed organisations (N=64, skipped: 0).

Provision of harm reduction services

Harm reduction services offered

The collected data provides a comprehensive overview of the availability of harm reduction services within community-based organisations, revealing insights into the prioritisation and distribution of these services. Service offered means that the service was available, i.e., it was possible to use it within the organisation surveyed.

The data indicates a strong emphasis on overdose prevention, with take-home naloxone (THN) being the most prevalent service on offer, available in 73.5% of organisations. This high availability underscores the critical importance placed on equipping individuals with the means to immediately respond to opioid overdoses.

Similarly, needle syringe provision (NSP), available in 66.7% of organisations, highlights a widespread commitment to reducing the transmission of infectious diseases such as HIV and Hepatitis C among people who use drugs. This service, along with 'peer-to-peer naloxone' found on offer in 63.3% of organisations, demonstrates a community-focused approach where individuals support each other, enhancing the reach and effectiveness of these interventions.

Conversely, the relatively low availability of heroin-assisted treatment (HAT) and drug checking services (DCSs), at 15.8% and 24.2% respectively, points to potential gaps in the harm reduction landscape. HAT, which involves supervised, medical administration of pharmaceutical-grade heroin, is a still controversial yet effective treatment for people who use heroin long-term and who have not benefited sufficiently from other treatments. Its limited availability in the surveyed services is indicative of regulatory challenges and societal resistance to such programmes. Similarly, the low availability of DCSs suggests a missed opportunity to further reduce harm by enabling people who use drugs to test substances for dangerous adulterants, helping to prevent overdoses and other adverse effects.

The data also sheds light on the broader support services offered by the respondents' organisations, such as housing and legal support, which are essential for the social stabilisation of people who use drugs. However, these services are less prevalent, with 'temporary housing' and 'long-term housing' available in only 31.6% and 27.8% of organisations, respectively. This indicates a need for more comprehensive support systems that address not only the immediate health concerns associated with drug use but also the underlying social determinants of health.

Overall, the data shows that the distribution of harm reduction services reflects a nuanced approach to addressing the complex needs of people who use drugs. While there is a commendable focus on lifesaving interventions, the data also highlights significant areas for improvement, particularly in providing comprehensive care and addressing the broader social and health needs of this population.

Harm reduction services delivered

Delivery of services means that the service was used by (a) client(s), that is, it addresses the utilisation rates of various harm reduction services, offering a snapshot of how different interventions are being accessed by people who use drugs.

The most prominently utilised service, as indicated by the data, is the NSP, with a usage rate of 64.9%. This high uptake highlights the critical role that NSPs play in harm reduction policies, primarily by mitigating the risks associated with infectious diseases transmitted through shared or unsterile syringes. Similarly, services related to Naloxone also show significant engagement. THN was used by 64.7% of clients, and peer-to-peer Naloxone by 66.7%, reflecting a strong community response to overdose prevention. However, other crucial services like drug consumption rooms (DCRs) and DCSs are delivered to a lesser extent, with rates of only 25.0% and 27.3% respectively. These lower figures may point to barriers such as limited availability, societal stigma, or a lack of awareness about the services. This underutilisation suggests a need for increased advocacy and education to enhance access and acceptance of DCRs.

The data also reveals moderate engagement with services aimed at safer drug use, such as safer inhalation kits and safer intranasal kits, utilised by 42.4% and 39.4% of clients, respectively. These rates indicate a substantial, yet not comprehensive, reach of these interventions, suggesting room for broader dissemination and education about the benefits of using such kits. Legal support, accessed by 50.9% of clients, highlights the ongoing legal challenges faced by people who use drugs, emphasising the importance of integrating legal aid into harm reduction services.

Interestingly, the data shows a slight disparity in the utilisation of officially endorsed versus unofficial Naloxone distribution, with rates of 47.1% and 53.3% respectively. This suggests more reliance on informal networks for accessing Naloxone, which could indicate barriers in the formal healthcare system and the need for more integrated service delivery models.

Lastly, housing services show relatively low utilisation, with long-term housing accessed by 27.8% and temporary housing by 34.2%. These figures underscore a significant gap in addressing the social determinants of health for this population, pointing to a pressing need for more robust housing support within harm reduction frameworks.

Number of harm reduction services

Service	Offered	Delivered	
Opioid agonist treatment (OAT)	13	11	84.6%
Heroin-assisted treatment (HAT)	3	1	33.3%
Needle syringe provision (NSP)	38	27	71.1%
Peer-to-peer NSP	28	21	75.0%
Safer intranasal kits	14	9	(64.3%)
Safer inhalation kits	17	9	(52.9%)
Official naloxone distribution	18	12	(66.7%)
Unofficial naloxone distribution	8	5	(62.5%)
Take-home naloxone (THN)	25	18	(72.0%)
Peer-to-peer naloxone	19	15	(78.9%)
Drug consumption room (DCR)	9	4	(44.4%)
Drug checking	8	4	(50.0%)
Temporary housing	12	7	(58.3%)
Long-term housing	10	7	(70.0%)
Income generation	10	5	(50.0%)
Legal support	25	17	(68.0%)

Table 2. The number of harm reduction services offered in the respondents' organisations and the proportion of services delivered.

Linkage of harm reduction services

Linkage of services is understood as providing referral(s) to another entity by the survey harm reduction service. The data provides a comprehensive picture of how community-based harm reduction services are connecting individuals to other critical services. The highest linkage rates are observed in OAT and HAT, at 78.4% and 79.0% respectively, indicating a strong focus on treatments directly addressing opioid dependence. The high number of referrals to HATs, however, is an issue that would require additional investigation, as such programmes are available only in a very few countries. It would, therefore, be necessary, to further investigate how the respondents understood the reported linkage. Notwithstanding, the data suggests that harm reduction programmes are effectively prioritising interventions that have a direct impact on the health outcomes of individuals with opioid dependency.

Conversely, the linkage rates for NSP and peer-to-peer NSP are notably lower, at 35.1% and 32.0% respectively. This could be related to high rates of direct provision of these services on-site, and the consequent lack of need

to use referrals. The moderate linkage rates for safer use kits—54.6% for intranasal and 45.5% for inhalation— as well as naloxone distribution, likely involve a similar logic.

On the other hand, the data shows a strong linkage to housing services, with 60.5% for temporary housing, 69.4% for long-term solutions, and a 52.0% linkage rate for income generation programmes. These figures are encouraging, as they suggest that harm reduction services are – at least to some extent – addressing broader social determinants of health, which can significantly impact the quality of life for people who use drugs.

Provision of harm reduction services in a comparative perspective

Analysis of the data on offered and linked services together offers an interesting picture of the relationships between these two ways of accessing harm reduction services either on-site or through linkage to other organisations.

For instance, OAT is available on-site in 25.5% of cases but is linked through referrals in 78.4% of cases, suggesting a strong reliance on external partnerships for this service. Similarly, HAT is rarely available on-site (15.8%) and is predominantly provided through referrals (79.0%). This pattern is consistent with services like drug checking and long-term housing, which are also primarily offered through referrals, with 69.7% and 69.4% respectively. Conversely, services such as NSP and THN are more frequently available on-site, with 66.7% and 73.5% respectively, indicating a more direct approach to accessibility at the point of contact in harm reduction facilities. This suggests that while some services necessitate broader network involvement and external resources, others are more effectively managed within the initial point of care, enhancing immediate access and support. The predominance of referral services over on-site availability highlights a collaborative network in the harm reduction ecosystem, emphasising the importance of interconnected services to address the complex needs of individuals. This approach not only extends the reach of harm reduction efforts but also integrates a wider range of specialised services that may not be feasible to provide directly within every organisation.

Provision of Services: Specific Health Interventions

Specific health interventions offered

The data provides a detailed snapshot of the availability of specific health services within community-based harm reduction organisations, highlighting significant disparities in the provision of these services. Notably, the most commonly available services are infectious disease education, information, and counselling, with a reported availability of 77.8%, and HIV testing at 67.8%. These figures suggest a strong emphasis on educational outreach and initial testing services, which are crucial for early detection and prevention efforts. However, there is a stark contrast in the availability of more specialised interventions such as Pre-exposure prophylaxis for HIV (PrEP) and Post-exposure prophylaxis for HIV (PEP) and STIs, which are directly available only in 15.6% and 11.1% of the organisations, respectively. This indicates a significant gap in the continuum of care necessary to effectively combat the spread of HIV. Additionally, services aimed at preventing vertical transmission of infections like HIV, syphilis, and hepatitis B show moderate availability, ranging from 36.8% to 46.2%, pointing to partial coverage in addressing mother-to-child transmission risks. The data also reveals a relatively lower availability of treatment services for HIV (15.7%) and other STIs and hepatitis, which underscores potential challenges in accessing comprehensive care post-diagnosis. This variability in service availability not only reflects the diverse priorities and resource allocations among harm reduction programmes but also underscores the critical need for enhancing service integration and availability to address all aspects of harm reduction effectively.

Provision of selected specific health interventions

Specific health interventions delivered

Starting with the more frequently utilised services, infectious disease education, information, and counselling were accessed by 74.6% of clients. This high uptake suggests a strong awareness and perceived value of educational interventions among clients, which is crucial for empowering individuals with knowledge to care for their health proactively. Similarly, the provision of condoms and lubricants was utilised by 76.7% of clients, underscoring their critical role in preventing the transmission of HIV and communicable diseases. The relatively high utilisation of these preventive measures indicates a successful integration of these services into the harm reduction programmes, likely facilitated by their immediate and tangible benefits in preventing disease transmission.

The low levels of utilisation of other crucial services, such as PrEP (11.1% of clients) and PEP (8.9%) can be attributed to the low on-site availability at harm reduction services. In a similar vein, moderate to low utilisation rates of preventing vertical transmission are related to the levels of availability of these services on-site in community-based harm reduction organisations

Figure 6. The provision of selected specific health interventions by the surveyed organisations (N=64, skipped: 0).

(35.7% for HIV, 29.0% for syphilis, and 30.8% for hepatitis B). These figures highlight potential gaps in reaching pregnant women within harm-reduction settings.

Testing services showed varied utilisation, with HIV testing at 62.7%, hepatitis C testing also at 62.7%, but STI testing lower at 44.2%. The relatively higher rates for HIV and hepatitis C testing could reflect targeted efforts and funding streams that prioritise these diseases, whereas the lower rate for STI testing is likely related to lower service availability in harm-reduction settings.

Linkage of specific health interventions

Based on the collected data, it is quite evident that there is a strong emphasis on services related to HIV and other sexually transmitted infections. For instance, the data shows that PrEP and PEP have the highest referral rates at 91.1% each.

Similarly, the data indicates substantial referral rates for other services aimed at preventing vertical transmission of infections from mother to child. The prevention of vertical transmission of HIV is noted at 64.3%, syphilis at 71.1%, and Hepatitis B (HBV) at 64.1%. These services are vital in reducing the incidence of congenital infections.

Vaccination services, such as Hepatitis B vaccination, which has a referral rate of 74.4%, also play a significant role in these community-based programmes. Vaccinations are a primary preventive measure that can significantly reduce the incidence of these infections in marginalised populations. Testing services form another critical component of the harm reduction strategy, as indicated by the data. HIV testing and STI testing are referred at rates of 50.9% and 67.3%, respectively. Hepatitis B and C testing have referral rates of 56.0% and 49.2%, respectively.

Treatment services are also very well-linked according to the data, with HIV treatment referrals at 90.2%, and treatments for HIV-associated tuberculosis at 87.5%. Treatment for STIs, HBV, and Hepatitis C (HCV) are referred at rates of 78.7%, 81.3%, and 77.6%, respectively. These high referral rates underscore the harm reduction services' role in not only prevention but also in ensuring the continuity of care for those who need further attention.

Provision of specific health interventions in a comparative perspective

From a comparative perspective, the data reveals a significant variance in the approach to service delivery across different health interventions. For instance, services such as infectious disease education, information, and counselling are predominantly available on-site (77.8%) compared to

referrals (34.9%). This suggests a strong in-house capability to educate and counsel on infectious diseases within the harm reduction services themselves. In contrast, more specialised services like PrEP and PEP show a reverse trend, with low on-site availability (15.6% and 11.1% respectively) and high referral rates (91.1% for both). This indicates that while the organisations recognise the importance of these treatments, they rely heavily on external entities for their provision. Similarly, treatments for HIV, Hepatitis B, and Hepatitis C also have significantly higher referral rates compared to on-site availability, highlighting potential gaps in direct service provision within harm reduction facilities. This data underscores the critical role of networked services and partnerships in delivering comprehensive health-care in community-based settings, especially for more complex medical interventions.

Provision of Services: Broader Health Interventions

Provision of broader health interventions

Figure 7. The provision of selected broader health interventions by the surveyed organisations (N=64, skipped: 0).

Broader health services offered

Figure 7 is a snapshot of the availability of various community-based harm reduction services within an organisation. The percentages reflect the extent to which each service is offered on-site, highlighting significant disparities in service provision. Notably, mental health care is the service most frequently available on-site, offered by 49.2% of the organisations. This suggests a strong recognition of the importance of mental health support in harm-reduction settings. In contrast, services such as safe abortion and those related to cervical cancer are very low, at 3.0% and 5.3% respectively, indicating critical gaps in reproductive health responses. The relatively higher availability of screening and treatment for hazardous and harmful alcohol and other substance use (38.3%) aligns with the core objectives of harm reduction programmes, yet the low availability of comprehensive reproductive health services underscores a significant shortfall in addressing all aspects of health that affect marginalised populations. This data not only sheds light on the current state of service provision but also underscores the need for a more holistic approach in harm reduction programmes to better meet the diverse needs of their clients.

Broader health services delivered

Mental health care services were utilised by 44.1% of clients, the highest among all services listed. This significant figure underscores the growing recognition of mental health as a critical component of overall health. The high utilisation rate may reflect both the increasing destigmatisation of mental health issues and the effectiveness of community-based approaches in providing accessible mental health support. It also highlights the ongoing need for robust mental health services that can address a wide range of issues within the community setting.

Screening and treatment for hazardous and harmful alcohol and other substance use, which had the second highest utilisation rate at 31.9%, reflect the pressing need for substance use and dependency services. It also suggests that these services are not only needed but are also likely well-integrated into the community, providing essential support to individuals struggling with dependency.

Contraception services, used by 28.3% of clients, represent another critical area of community health. The higher utilisation rate here compared to conception and pregnancy care might suggest a greater general acceptance or demand for contraceptive services, or it could indicate effective community outreach and education about the benefits of contraception. This figure aligns with broader public health goals aimed at reducing unintended pregnancies and empowering individuals with choices regarding their reproductive health.

Further, regarding conception and pregnancy care, which was utilised by 22.7% of clients, the data suggests a significant engagement with services aimed at supporting reproductive health. This level of utilisation highlights the importance of accessible reproductive health services in community settings, potentially indicating a gap in mainstream healthcare systems that these community services are filling.

TB prevention, screening, diagnosis, and treatment services were utilised by 16.3% of clients. This relatively robust engagement might indicate a high burden of TB within the community or effective community health strategies that prioritise TB due to its potential severity and the public health necessity of controlling its spread.

Finally, the prevention, assessment, and treatment of cervical cancer had a notably lower utilisation rate at 5.3%. This is related to the low availability of this service in harm reduction settings, similar to safe abortion services, which were accessed by 6.1% of clients.

Linkage of broader health services

The data shows several key insights emerge about the priorities and challenges within harm reduction linkages. Firstly, the high percentages of refer-

rals for services like safe abortion (97.0%) and tuberculosis-related services (93.0%) suggest a robust network and a strong emphasis on linking individuals to these critical services. This could be indicative of the recognition of the immediate and severe consequences of not addressing these needs promptly and effectively within vulnerable populations. The high linkage rate for cervical cancer services (92.1%) similarly underscores an awareness of the importance of preventive care, which can prevent more severe health issues down the line.

Conversely, the relatively lower linkage rates for services like contraception (69.6%) and mental health care (69.5%) could point to several potential gaps or challenges but could also be simply linked to higher levels of provision of these services within harm reduction organisations.

The data also speaks to the broader role of harm reduction programs in public health. By providing linkages to such a wide array of services, these programs act not only as a direct response to harm associated with substance use and punitive policies but also as a crucial entry point into the healthcare system for marginalised individuals who might otherwise remain outside its reach.

Furthermore, the variation in linkage rates across different services highlights the need for targeted improvements in harm reduction strategies. For instance, enhancing partnerships with mental health and reproductive health providers could be a strategic focus for increasing the linkage rates in these areas. Additionally, these figures could serve as a baseline for evaluating the impact of policy changes, funding increases, or new initiatives aimed at improving the integration of harm reduction services with broader healthcare systems.

Provision of broader health interventions in a comparative perspective

The data on the availability of broader health services in the context of harm reduction reveals a clear pattern: a significant portion of services, particularly those requiring specialised care, are more commonly offered through referrals rather than directly on-site. For instance, the provision of safe abortion services is overwhelmingly through referral (97%) compared to on-site availability (3%), highlighting a potential gap in immediate access to this critical service within the community-based harm reduction setting. Similarly, the prevention, assessment, and treatment of cervical cancer show a stark contrast, with a mere 5.3% of services available on-site versus a staggering 92.1% offered through referrals. This trend suggests a reliance on external entities for specialised healthcare services, which could be attributed to the need for specialised equipment, expertise, or both, that are likely not within the financial reach of harm reduction organisations.

Conversely, mental health care shows a relatively higher on-site availability (49.2%) compared to other services, though referrals still account for a significant portion (69.59%). This indicates a better but still suboptimal integration of mental health services within harm reduction services, possibly reflecting an increasing recognition of mental health's importance but also highlighting the ongoing challenges in fully embedding these services into low-threshold care settings.

The data underscores a broader health system challenge: ensuring comprehensive, immediate access to a range of critical health services. While referrals are an essential component of a connected and specialised health-care system, the heavy reliance on them for services such as safe abortion and cervical cancer treatment raises questions about accessibility, potential delays in care, and the continuity of patient care. It suggests a need for health systems to further integrate specialised services on-site or develop stronger, more efficient referral networks that minimise barriers to access and ensure timely, coordinated care.

Provision of Services: The Settings

The survey data reveals a broad spectrum of settings that organisations have utilised to provide harm reduction services. These include outreach programmes, drop-in or low-threshold centres, peer-to-peer mode of delivery, online or e-services, mobile units, prison settings, and other specified environments such as night shelters, DCRs, and social work settings. Each of these settings caters to different aspects of accessibility and specific needs of people who use drugs.

Settings of service provision

Figure 8. The settings of service provision in surveyed organisations (N=64, skipped: 0).

Outreach programmes, as indicated in the survey, are a predominant mode of service delivery (82.8%, 53 respondents), emphasising the proactive steps organisations take to reach individuals in their own environments. This approach is particularly effective in engaging those who might not seek support actively due to stigma or lack of awareness about available services. The flexibility of outreach programmes allows harm reduction services to be extended into various community locations, thereby increasing their reach and impact.

Drop-in or low-threshold centres are another significant setting highlighted by the respondents, with 71.9% (46) respondents reporting delivering services in such spaces. These spaces are vital, as they provide a safe, welcoming space where individuals can access services without the need for appointments or formal intake processes, hence reducing entry barriers. Peer-to-peer services underscore the importance of community and mutual

support among individuals who use drugs and is reported by 68.8% (44) respondents. By leveraging the living and lived experiences of peers, these programmes foster a sense of trust and understanding that is often lacking in traditional healthcare settings. This approach not only empowers individuals but also embeds harm reduction practices within the community, enhancing their adequacy and relevance.

The inclusion of online or e-services (46.9%, 30 respondents) reflects the modernisation of harm reduction strategies to incorporate digital tools and platforms. This mode of service delivery has become increasingly important, particularly in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, as it allows for the continuation of support and counselling services despite physical distancing measures. It also increases accessibility for individuals who may face geographical or mobility barriers.

Mobile units, a critical component of the harm reduction ecosystem bringing services directly to the communities and individuals in need, are less prevalent settings of service delivery among the surveyed organisations, with 45.3% (29) respondents mentioning them. Mobile units are particularly effective in reaching underserved or remote areas where fixed-site services may not be available. They can offer a range of services, including needle exchange, basic healthcare, and overdose prevention, making them a versatile tool in the harm reduction arsenal.

The survey also notes the provision of services in specialised settings such as prisons, with the data showing that the delivery of services in this setting is significantly limited – only 32.8% (21) respondents reported delivering services in prisons. Scaling up service delivery in prisons is crucial as people in prison and other enclosed settings are often at higher risk of harm, including the transmission of infectious diseases. Providing harm reduction services in prisons can significantly impact public health and safety by reducing the risk of disease transmission and supporting the health of individuals in prison.

Concerning the number/range of settings where each of the surveyed organisations delivers its services, the data shows a considerable variance.

Number of settings of service delivery

Figure 9. The number of settings of service delivery per surveyed organisation (N=64, skipped: 0).

The data shows that the majority of organisations operate across multiple settings, which suggests a versatile approach to service delivery. Specifically, the data shows that 16 organisations (25%) operate in four settings, and 15 organisations (23.4%) operate in three settings. This indicates that a significant proportion of harm reduction services are not limited to a single service delivery point but are instead spreading their resources across various environments to maximise their reach and impact. The presence of organisations in multiple settings can be interpreted as a strategic decision to enhance service accessibility and effectiveness. By operating in various settings, harm reduction services can access different underserved groups who may require harm reduction services. For instance, operating in settings such as community centres or mobile units can facilitate a more significant community presence and foster a deeper connection with the community members, potentially leading to higher engagement and better health outcomes.

Moreover, the data reveals that 13 organisations (20.3%) provide services in five settings, and a smaller number, 7 organisations (10.9%), extend their services to six settings. This wide range of service locations underscores the comprehensive approach these organisations are taking to address the complex needs of people who use drugs. It also reflects a robust framework aimed at creating multiple touchpoints for individuals seeking support, thereby increasing the likelihood of successful interventions.

On the lower end of the spectrum, the data shows that fewer organisations operate in either one or seven settings, with six organisations (9.4%) and two organisations (3.1%) respectively. This indicates that operating at either extreme is less common, possibly due to resource limitations or strategic choices based on community needs and organisational capacity. Organisations operating in only one setting might be focusing their efforts on a particular community or type of service, which could be due to funding restrictions, specific expertise, or a targeted intervention strategy.

Outreach and barriers to outreach

Another essential aspect of community-based harm reduction services operation is the extent to which they can reach specific sub-groups of clients with their services. Figure 10 presents a detailed breakdown of the outreach efforts of the surveyed services in 2022. This data is crucial for understanding the reach and impact of harm reduction strategies across diverse groups, particularly those most marginalised.

Figure 10.
Sub-populations reached by the surveyed harm reduction organisations in 2022 (N=64, skipped: 0).

Sub-populations reached in 2022

The data reveals a significant outreach to people who inject opiates, with 87.5% of organisations reaching this group, underscoring the dominant 'traditional' focus on people using opioids. Similarly, substantial outreach efforts are directed towards people who inject stimulants or new psychoactive substances (81.3%) and those who inhale stimulants like cocaine or crack (79.7%), highlighting the broad spectrum of substances used that are being addressed by harm reduction services. Notably, women who use drugs and LGBTQI individuals are also significantly reached, with outreach percentages of 82.8% and 71.9%, respectively, indicating efforts to ensure an inclusive approach that considers the unique intersectionalities and needs of these populations.

However, the data also points to areas where outreach could be strengthened. For instance, young people who use drugs and migrants who use drugs without legal rights to assistance are among the least reached populations, with outreach percentages of 35.9% and 43.8%, respectively. This gap in service delivery to young users is particularly concerning, given the potential for early interventions to prevent risks and harm is a long-term perspective. Similarly, the low outreach to migrants without legal rights suggests a critical need for targeted strategies to overcome barriers to access, which can include fear of deportation or lack of awareness about available services.

The outreach to people in prison settings (43.8%) also raises important considerations. Given the high risk of substance use and the spread of infectious diseases within prisons, the relatively low outreach percentage suggests a missed opportunity for harm reduction interventions in these environments. This gap underscores the need for policies and programmes that facilitate the delivery of harm reduction services within the criminal justice system, recognising the importance of addressing substance use as a public health issue rather than a criminal matter.

Moreover, the data on outreach to people experiencing homelessness (78.1%) and sex workers (76.6%) reflect a recognition of the complex interplay between substance use and social determinants of health. These populations often face multiple barriers to accessing health services, including stigma, discrimination, and lack of stable housing. The relatively high outreach percentages to these groups suggest that harm reduction services are making efforts to reach populations that are not only at increased risk of substance use-related harms but also often marginalised from mainstream health and social services.

Overall, it is clear that harm reduction services are making significant efforts to reach a diverse range of sub-populations. However, the data also highlights critical gaps in service delivery to young people, migrants without legal rights, and individuals in prison settings. Addressing these gaps requires innovative outreach strategies and policy reforms that ensure

harm reduction services are accessible to all individuals at risk, regardless of their age, legal status, or incarceration. Ultimately, the data underscores the importance of continued investment in harm reduction services as a key component of public health strategies to mitigate the impacts of substance use and punitive policies across all segments of society.

To dive deeper into the topic of harm reduction outreach, the data shows a detailed picture of the barriers that hinder the outreach of harm reduction services to various subpopulations, shedding light on the multifaceted challenges faced by organisations in reaching out to those in need of harm reduction services.

Figure 11. The barriers to outreach to subpopulations with harm reduction services by the surveyed organisations (N=64, skipped: 0).

Barriers to outreach to subpopulations with harm reduction services

The survey responses, which encompass a wide range of subpopulations from people who inject opiates to migrants who use drugs with no legal rights to assistance, reveal a complex interplay of legal, capacity-related, and societal issues that collectively impede the effective delivery of these crucial services. In total, respondents identified 485 barriers across 16 sub-populations and eight barrier categories. Most of the survey organisations do not reach out to specific populations simply because they are not the target groups of their services (157 responses, 32.4%).

Among the specific barriers, lack of funding was mentioned most often (70 times, 14.4%), closely followed by limited capacity of services/staff (69 times, 14.2%), a lack of meaningful involvement with this community (66 times, 13.6%) and legal issues (61 times, 12.6%). Service accessibility was by far the most rarely mentioned barrier (20 times, 4.1%), while stigma and lack of specific knowledge/guidelines were reported by less than ten per cent of respondents (48 times; 9.9% and 42 times, 8.7%, respectively).

Moreover, the option 'other' was chosen by the respondents relatively often (109 times, 22.5%). The analysis of additional information provided by the

respondents reveals additional challenges that community-based harm organisations struggle with.

One significant barrier highlighted is the legal and bureaucratic constraints, particularly in accessing populations within controlled environments like prisons. For instance, the necessity to obtain permission from the appropriate ministry to work in prisons underscores a systemic barrier that can delay or prevent the implementation of harm reduction services where they are critically needed. Another notable challenge is reaching minors and young people, particularly those under 18 years old. The data reveals a hesitancy or outright legal barriers to providing services to this group, often due to legal issues related to the provision of health services to minors without parental consent. The mention of reaching minors in party settings but not formally asking their age highlights an informal approach that is being implemented to overcome the systemic barriers.

In general, the distribution of barriers across subpopulations does not seem to exhibit any clear pattern. However, in the case of 7 specific sub-groups, one dominant barrier to reaching out by harm reduction programmes can be identified (mentioned by at least 25% of respondents not reaching out to the respective population), as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. The dominant barriers preventing the surveyed harm reduction organisations from reaching out to specific sub-populations.

Dominant barriers to reaching sub-populations with harm reduction services

Subpopulation	Dominant barrier	% respondents
People who inhale opiates	Lack of meaningful involvement with this community	25% (6/24)
People who inhale stimulants (cocaine/crack)	Lack of funding	25% (5/20)
People who use intranasal amphetamines/cocaine/ cathinone, etc.	Lack of funding	25% (6/24)
People experiencing homelessness	Limited capacity of services/ staff	28,6% (6/21)
Young people who use drugs (under 18 years of age)	Legal issues (punitive/restrictive laws & policies)	40,5% (17/42)
Ageing people who use drugs (above 50 years of age)	Lack of meaningful involvement with this community	26,3% (5/19)
People in prison settings	Legal issues (punitive/restrictive laws & policies)	29,4% (10/34)

⁶ Mentioned by at least 15% of respondents.

From another perspective, the limited capacity of services/ staff was mentioned as a major barrier⁶ across 10/16 specific sub-populations, along with lack of funding (also 10/16 populations). A lack of meaningful involvement with this community seems to be a significant challenge in nine sub-populations, followed by legal issues (7 populations). Lack of specific knowledge/guidelines in the organisation and stigma-related reluctance of potential clients to identify as a person who uses drugs were mentioned as barriers across five subpopulations each, and service accessibility was not considered a significant barrier in any of the 16 examined groups.

One of the most striking insights from the survey is the significant role that legal issues play in restricting access to harm reduction services. Legal barriers, often in the form of punitive or restrictive laws and policies, emerge as a formidable obstacle, particularly for populations such as youth who use drugs and individuals in prison settings. These legal constraints not only limit the scope of services that organisations can offer but also likely create an environment of fear and mistrust among those who most need these services.

Another critical barrier highlighted in the survey is the limited capacity of services and staff. These capacity issues are not merely logistical but can deeply impact the quality and reach of harm reduction services. Furthermore, the survey responses underscore the critical issue of funding, which is likely tightly related to the capacity problems. The lack of financial resources is a pervasive challenge that affects nearly every aspect of harm reduction service delivery. From the inability to expand services to meet the growing needs of diverse populations to the struggle to maintain existing programmes amidst financial constraints, the scarcity of funding emerges as a key barrier to achieving comprehensive harm reduction outreach. This financial limitation not only affects the sustainability of programmes but also limits the ability of organisations to innovate and adapt to the evolving needs of the communities they serve.

The survey also brings to light the impact of stigma-related barriers. The stigma associated with drug use, deeply ingrained in societal attitudes, and reinforced by legal and policy frameworks, hinders the outreach efforts of harm reduction services. Stigma not only deters individuals from accessing services but also influences the allocation of resources and the development of policies that could support more effective harm reduction strategies.

The collected data also includes significant insights into the barriers faced by people who use drugs in accessing services for infectious diseases such as HIV, hepatitis C virus (HCV), hepatitis B virus (HBV), and sexually transmitted infections (STIs).

The most prominent barrier, as indicated by the data, is a stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs, which affects a sub-

stantial proportion of potential clients across all the mentioned services. Specifically, 56.9% for HIV services, 55.9% for HCV services, 45.0% for HBV services, and 50.8% for STI services. This high percentage underscores the pervasive impact of stigma on the willingness of individuals to seek necessary healthcare services.

Main challenges in reaching out with infectious diseases services

Figure 12. The main challenges in reaching out to people who use drugs with infectious diseases services in respondents' countries (N=64, skipped: 0).

Stigma, as a social phenomenon, involves the negative labelling and discriminatory treatment of individuals based on certain characteristics or behaviours, in this case, drug use. The reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs and to seek help for infectious diseases is rooted in the fear of social judgement, discrimination, and potential ostracism from both society and healthcare settings. The implications of stigma as a barrier to accessing services are profound. Not only does it prevent individuals from accessing health services, but they also contribute to the ongoing transmission of infectious diseases within these communities. The reluctance to seek care due to stigma means that many infections go undiagnosed and untreated, leading to worse health outcomes for the individual and greater public health risks. This is particularly critical in the context of diseases like HIV and hepatitis, which require timely diagnosis and consistent treatment to manage effectively and prevent transmission.

Funding constraints are also repeatedly highlighted as a major hurdle. Insufficient funding affects all aspects of service provision – from the availability of resources and personnel to the scope of programmes that can be offered. This financial barrier is a recurring theme that underscores the challenges faced by health services in sustaining and scaling up their operations to meet the needs of people who use drugs effectively.

Furthermore, the survey data indicates a substantial limitation in the capacity of services and staff to handle the needs of people who use drugs. The deficiency in specialised training and expertise among healthcare providers can lead to inadequate service delivery, leaving the health needs of individuals unmet.

Accessibility issues also emerge as a significant barrier, with factors such as inconvenient location, restrictive opening hours, and language barriers limiting the reach of services to people who use drugs. These logistical challenges are crucial as they directly affect the ability of individuals to access prevention, testing, and treatment services, which are essential for controlling the spread of infectious diseases within this population. This can be aggravated by the lack of meaningful involvement with the community of people who use drugs. Engagement with the community is not only about providing services but also about building trust and understanding the specific needs and circumstances of individuals. Without their involvement, services may not be appropriately tailored or accepted, thereby reducing their effectiveness.

With respect to the main barriers across specific services, in all but one (HBV vaccination is an exception), stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs emerges as a consistently the most significant barrier, highlighting the pervasive impact of stigma on accessing harm reduction and infectious disease services. Lack of funding and limited capacity of services/staff are also recurrent significant challenges, indicating resource constraints as a major hurdle in service delivery.

The main challenges in reaching out

Service type	Main challenges
HIV Prevention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (60.9%) ■ Lack of funding (46.9%)
HIV Testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (57.8%) ■ Lack of funding (40.6%)
HIV Treatment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (50.00%) ■ Service accessibility (28.1%)
HCV Prevention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (57.8%) ■ Lack of funding (43.8%)
HCV Testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (54.7%) ■ Limited capacity of services/staff (34.4%)
HCV Treatment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (53.1%) ■ Service accessibility (31.3%)
HBV Prevention (Excluding Vaccination)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (50.00%) ■ Limited capacity of services/staff (34.4%)
HBV Vaccination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Other factors (32.81%) ■ Service accessibility (31.3%)
HBV Testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (43.75%) ■ Limited capacity of services/staff (35.9%)
HBV Care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (43.75%) ■ Other factors (35.9%)
STI Prevention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (54.69%) ■ Lack of funding (35.9%)
STI Testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (50.00%) ■ Limited capacity of services/staff (31.3%)
STI Treatment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Stigma-related reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs (45.3%) ■ Service accessibility (28.1%)

Table 4. The main challenges in reaching out to people who use drugs with specific infectious diseases services in respondents' countries (N=64, skipped:0).

Cooperation for person-centred approach and continuity of care

Figure 13 provides an overview of the cooperation levels between harm reduction services and various other services aimed at improving the quality of life for people who use drugs. The data includes information on twenty-two different services, ranging from primary health care to services focusing on specific populations like migrants or people living with HIV. A closer analysis of the data reveals several key insights into the current state of cooperation between harm reduction services and other sectors.

The most successful collaborations, as indicated by the highest percentages of 'Yes, and cooperation is good,' are with services focusing on people living with HIV, where 70.3% of respondents reported good cooperation. This high level of effective collaboration likely reflects a well-established understanding of the needs of PLHIV individuals among harm reduction services, coupled with a strong network of support that includes healthcare providers and community organisations specialising in HIV care.

Another strong area of cooperation is with services providing food and/or clothing, where 57.8% of respondents indicated good cooperation. This suggests that harm reduction services are effectively integrated with basic need providers, ensuring that individuals who use drugs have access to essential resources, which can be crucial for their overall stability and well-being.

Dependency treatment centres, both inpatient (43.8%) and outpatient (45.3%), also show relatively high levels of good cooperation. These figures indicate a robust linkage between harm reduction initiatives and treatment facilities, which is vital for a comprehensive approach to reintegration.

On the other end of the spectrum, the collaborations with public labour and employment offices and work reintegration and training programmes are among the most challenging. Only 12.5% and 15.6% of respondents, respectively, reported good cooperation with these services. These low percentages highlight significant barriers in integrating harm reduction clients into the workforce and suggest systemic issues such as stigma, lack of tailored job training programmes, and possibly insufficient advocacy within the employment sectors.

Cooperation of harm reduction services with other services to ensure person-centred approach

Figure 13. The extent to which surveyed harm reduction services cooperate with other services to ensure person-centred approach for the improvement of the quality of life of people who use drugs (N=64, skipped: 0).

Prison settings also show relatively poor cooperation, with only 17.2% of respondents indicating that cooperation is good. This suggests challenges in implementing effective harm reduction strategies within the correctional system, possibly due to regulatory restrictions, lack of resources, or differing priorities in the management of people in prison settings who use drugs. Another notable aspect is the relatively high percentage of ‘I do not know’ responses for several services, including services focusing on sexual and reproductive rights, services providing support for survivors of violence, and services focusing on young people. This uncertainty could indicate a lack of awareness or communication between harm reduction services and these other sectors, suggesting that enhancing knowledge and information exchange could foster better cooperation.

The data also reveals a concerning lack of existence of certain services, as indicated by the responses for ‘No, such services do not exist.’ This is particularly evident in services focusing on chemsex, where 18.8% of respondents indicated the non-existence of such services, and in services focusing on ageing people, with 23.4% indicating the same. This highlights significant gaps in the service landscape, particularly for niche or emerging needs within the population of people who use drugs.

The insights from the data suggest that while harm reduction services are successfully collaborating with health-focused and basic needs services, there is a critical need for improvement in sectors that provide social and economic reintegration support. The varying levels of cooperation across different services underscore the need for a more integrated and holistic approach to harm reduction. Enhancing cooperation, especially in areas where it is currently lacking or challenging, could lead to more comprehensive support for people who use drugs, addressing not only their immediate health needs but also their broader social and economic well-being.

Cooperation with other services to ensure the continuity of care

Figure 14. The cooperation of the surveyed organisations with other services to ensure the continuity of care for clients testing positively for infectious diseases.

Besides ensuring the person-centred approach for the improvement of the quality of life of people who use drugs, collaboration for the continuity of care is also crucial. Figure 14 provides a picture of the cooperation between harm reduction services and various other healthcare and community services to ensure continuity of care for clients testing positively for infectious diseases such as HIV, HCV, HBV, and STIs.

The data shows significant levels of collaboration across different service types, which is essential for a holistic approach to care. The highest percentages of cooperation are observed with hospitals and harm reduction services or community centres, particularly in the context of HIV, where the cooperation rates are 96.1% and 96.2% respectively. This high level of integration with hospitals is critical as these institutions often serve as the primary point of care for many individuals, providing not only treatment but also access to specialised services that can manage complex health conditions effectively.

Drug treatment centres also show substantial cooperation, especially for HIV (93.5%) and HCV (89.1%), underscoring the importance of integrating dependency treatment with infectious disease care.

The cooperation with specialised clinics such as gastroenterology, infectious diseases, and sexual health is notably high for HCV (94.4%) but less so for HBV (64.8%) and STIs (70.4%). This variation could reflect the perceived urgency and availability of specialised care for these conditions, with HCV possibly receiving more attention due to its severe long-term health implications if left untreated.

General practitioners (GPs) and pharmacies show lower cooperation percentages across all diseases compared to hospitals and specialised clinics. For example, cooperation with GPs ranges from 62.9% for HBV to 85.7% for HIV. This might indicate potential gaps in the primary care sector's involvement in managing infectious diseases among people who use drugs, possibly due to a lack of resources, specialised knowledge, or prioritisation of this population in general practice settings.

Figure 15. The challenges in ensuring continuity of care through cooperation with health services (N=64, skipped: 0)

Challenges in ensuring the continuity of care

The data on barriers faced by harm reduction services in ensuring continuity of care for people who use drugs in need of infectious disease services provides interesting insights into reasons why the continuity of care may be insufficient in many contexts.

A striking 87.5% of respondents identified stigma regarding the history of drug use and/or minority status as a major barrier. This high percentage once again highlights the problem of stigma within healthcare and social settings, which can often lead to discrimination against people who use drugs, thereby limiting their access to necessary healthcare services.

Stigma not only affects the way individuals are treated within healthcare settings but also influences their willingness to seek out care, fearing judgment or mistreatment. This barrier is particularly concerning as it suggests a deep-rooted prejudice that can undermine the effectiveness of harm reduction and health services care in the context of continuity of care.

Another significant barrier, as identified by 48.4% of respondents, is the limitation of treatment or care to individuals with health insurance, alongside a similar percentage noting the low accessibility of specialist services. These findings highlight systemic issues within healthcare systems that restrict access to necessary treatments. For people who use drugs, who often face socio-economic disadvantages, these barriers can be particularly prohibitive, preventing them from receiving consistent and comprehensive care for infectious diseases.

The issue of ineligibility for treatment or care for people currently or recently using drugs, noted by 45.3% of respondents, points to another systemic barrier where policies and practices within health services may directly exclude people who use drugs from receiving care. Such policies not only fail to recognise the complex nature of substance use and dependency as a condition that requires integrated approaches based on reducing harm, but they also violate principles of medical ethics which emphasise non-discrimination and equity in healthcare.

Financial and procedural barriers are also significant, with 26.6% of respondents indicating that treatment and care are not reimbursed, and an additional 18.8% pointing out that confirmatory testing requires a prescription, which can be a hurdle in accessing necessary diagnostic services. These financial and procedural barriers further complicate the care continuum, making it difficult for people who use drugs to obtain consistent and effective treatment for infectious diseases.

Involvement of people with lived / living experience

The involvement of people who use drugs in services is essential to ensure the adequacy, effectiveness and high quality of interventions. The data presented in Figure 16 shows the extent to which people with lived and/or living experience of drug use are involved in the organisation of harm reduction services. This involvement is measured across various dimensions of organisational operations, including governance, design/planning of services/programmes, implementation of services/programmes, and monitoring and evaluation of services/programmes.

Involvement of people with experience of drug use in the organisation

The highest level of involvement is observed in the implementation of services/programmes, where 46.9% of respondents indicated that people with lived or living experience of drug use are involved 'To a great extent.' This is followed by the design/planning of services/programmes, with 42.2% of organisations reporting significant involvement. These figures suggest a strong recognition of the value that lived experience brings to the practical aspects of harm reduction services, emphasising the importance of incorporating first-hand insights into both the planning and execution stages of service delivery.

In contrast, the involvement of people with lived experience in governance and monitoring and evaluation appears to be less pronounced. While 29.7% of respondents reported a high degree of involvement in governance, this area, along with monitoring and evaluation (34.4%), shows a more moderate level of engagement. This discrepancy may highlight potential barriers

Figure 16. The extent of involvement of people with lived and/or living experience of drug use in the organisation of harm reduction services in the surveyed organisations.

or challenges in integrating individuals with lived experience into more strategic or evaluative roles within organisations. It could reflect a need for greater support, training, or resources to empower these individuals to contribute effectively at all levels of organisational operation.

The data also reveals a significant portion of organisations where involvement is reported as 'To a small extent' or 'Not at all,' particularly in governance (46.9%) and the design/planning of services/programmes (26.6%).

These figures underscore the ongoing challenges and resistance that may exist within some organisations towards fully embracing the contributions of people with lived experience. It suggests that despite the recognised value of these perspectives, systemic or cultural barriers may still hinder their full integration and influence within harm reduction services.

Interestingly, the option 'I do not know' received 0.00% across all categories, indicating a clear awareness among respondents of the level of involvement of people with lived experience within their organisations.

This awareness is a positive sign, suggesting that organisations are at least acknowledging the importance of this issue, even if actual levels of involvement vary.

The effectiveness of harm reduction services is significantly influenced by the extent to which these services incorporate the perspectives and experiences of those they aim to serve. The data suggests that while there is a significant movement towards involving people with lived experience in harm reduction services, there remains room for improvement, especially in governance and monitoring/evaluation. The varying degrees of involvement across different organisational functions highlight the complexity of fully integrating perspectives of people who use drugs into harm reduction efforts. It underscores the need for continued advocacy, policy development, and organisational change to ensure that the invaluable insights of individuals with lived experience are not only recognised but are also leveraged to enhance the effectiveness, relevance, and compassion of harm reduction services. As harm reduction continues to evolve as a critical component of public health strategies for addressing drug use, this data serves as an important benchmark for assessing progress and identifying areas for further growth and inclusion.

Paid versus voluntary involvement of people with experience of drug use

Figure 17. Paid versus voluntary involvement of people with lived and/or living experience of drug use in harm reduction services in the surveyed organisations (N=64, skipped: 0).

Besides the areas of services operation where people who use drugs are involved in harm reduction services, it is also crucial to understand the dynamics between volunteerism and paid employment in the context of harm reduction services. Figure 17 shows the types of involvement of people with lived and/or living experience of drug use in harm reduction services within an organisation.

The data shows clearly that the most significant portion of individuals with drug use experience are involved in harm reduction services primarily as volunteers rather than as paid staff. Specifically, 32.8% of the surveyed organisations indicated that people who use drugs are involved 'In vast majority (>85%) as volunteers (no work contract and/or no payment)', and an additional 10.9% stated they are involved 'In majority (>50%) as volunteers'. This suggests that over 43% of the community-based harm reduction services rely heavily on volunteers with lived and leaving experience for delivering harm reduction services. This high level of volunteer involvement could be indicative of several factors including budget constraints within organisations, the altruistic motivations of the volunteers.

Conversely, the data also shows that 29.7% of the organisations involve individuals with drug use experience predominantly as paid staff (18.8% 'In vast majority (>85%) as paid staff' and 10.9% 'In majority (>50%) as paid staff'). This indicates a substantial reliance on paid employment for individuals with lived experience in nearly a third of the surveyed organisations. The employment of people who use drugs in paid roles could reflect an acknowledgement of the professional value these individuals bring to harm reduction

services, possibly due to their unique insights and ability to foster trust with service users.

The category ‘To the same extent as volunteers and paid staff’ accounts for 26.6% of the responses, highlighting that a significant portion of organisations maintain a balanced approach in engaging people with drug use experience. This balanced approach might be part of a broader strategy to maximise the benefits of both lived experience and professional employment in service delivery.

Analysing these figures, it is crucial to consider the implications of these staffing strategies on the effectiveness and sustainability of harm reduction programmes. The heavy reliance on volunteers might pose challenges such as high turnover rates, potentially lower levels of training compared to paid staff, and sustainability issues if volunteer motivation wears off. On the other hand, employing individuals with lived experience as paid staff could enhance programme stability and provide economic opportunities to a marginalised population, thereby supporting their life’s quality improvement and social reintegration.

Moreover, the integration of people with lived experience in harm reduction services, whether as volunteers or paid staff, is a critical component of a comprehensive approach to harm reduction. It not only empowers these individuals by acknowledging their valuable contributions but also enhances the services provided. Their involvement can lead to more culturally competent and responsive services that effectively address the needs and preferences of people who use drugs.

Figure 18. Ways of achieving the involvement of people who use drugs in surveyed organisations (N=64, skipped: 0).

Ways of achieving the involvement of people who use drugs

The data presented in Figure 18 shows the various methods through which people with lived or living experience of drug use are involved in the planning and evaluation of harm reduction services within surveyed organisations.

The most striking insight is the high percentage of organisations that involve people who use drugs through informal feedback (67.2%) and as staff members (65.6%). These methods suggest a significant shift towards integrating people with living and lived experience not just as beneficiaries of services but as active participants and contributors in the operational and decision-making processes of harm reduction programmes. The involvement of people who use drugs as staff members, in particular, indicates a progressive move towards empowerment and recognition of the expertise that comes from personal experience with drug use.

The data also shows that 50% of the organisations cooperate with networks of people who use drugs. This cooperation likely facilitates a broader community engagement, ensuring that the harm reduction services are not only tailored to individual needs but also embedded within the wider social context of the drug-using community. Such networks can provide a platform for collective advocacy and support, enhancing the reach and impact of harm reduction efforts.

Interestingly, 46.9% of respondents indicated that their organisation is community-led, hence boosting the involvement of people who use drugs. This model is particularly effective in building trust and accountability, as it aligns the organisation's objectives directly with the community's needs and aspirations.

The use of anonymous surveys (40.6%) as a method of involving people who use drugs also stands out. This approach allows for the collection of honest feedback without fear of reprisal or stigma, providing organisations with clear insights into the effectiveness and areas for improvement of their services.

The data also reveals that a small percentage (4.7%) of organisations report a complete lack of involvement of people who use drugs in their planning or evaluation processes. This could be indicative of traditional models of service delivery that might benefit from modern harm reduction philosophies that advocate for the inclusion of service users in governance and oversight.

National level challenges

Challenging areas in the context of prevention, diagnosis, treatment and care

Table 5. The challenging areas in the context of prevention, diagnosis, treatment and care of communicable diseases among people who use drugs in the respondents' countries (N=64, skipped: 0).

Answer Choices	Responses	
contextual factors		
<u>Punitive laws, policies and practices</u>	54,7%	35
<u>Stigma and discrimination</u>	78,1%	50
Community empowerment	29,7%	19
Violence	20,3%	13
access to harm reduction interventions		
Opioid agonist treatment (OAT)	20,3%	13
<u>Heroin assisted treatment (HAT)</u>	31,3%	20
Needle syringe provision (NSP)	7,8%	5
Peer-to-peer needle syringe provision (peer-to-peer NSP)	4,7%	3
Safer intranasal kits	4,7%	3
Safer inhalation kits	9,4%	6
Officially endorsed naloxone distribution (including prescription)	12,5%	8
Unofficial naloxone distribution	7,8%	5
Take-home naloxone (THN)	15,6%	10
Peer-to-peer naloxone	12,5%	8
<u>Drug consumption room (DCR)</u>	34,4%	22
<u>Drug checking</u>	32,8%	21
Temporary housing (e.g., night shelter)	21,9%	14
<u>Long-term housing (e.g., social housing, housing first)</u>	37,5%	24
Income generation for PWUD	21,9%	14
Legal support	15,6%	10
access to specific health interventions		
Infectious diseases education, information, counselling	3,1%	2
Condoms and lubricant	0,0%	0
Pre-exposure prophylaxis for HIV (PrEP)	12,5%	8
Post-exposure prophylaxis for HIV and STIs (PEP)	10,9%	7
Prevention of vertical transmission of HIV	3,1%	2
Prevention of vertical transmission of syphilis	0,0%	0
Prevention of vertical transmission of HBV	0,0%	0
Hepatitis B vaccination	4,7%	3
Addressing chemsex	17,2%	11
HIV testing	4,7%	3
STI testing	3,1%	2
Hepatitis B testing	1,6%	1
Hepatitis C testing	0,0%	0
HIV treatment	3,1%	2
Screening, diagnosis, treatment and prevention of HIV associated TB	3,1%	2
STI treatment	3,1%	2
HBV treatment	3,1%	2
HCV treatment	12,5%	8
access to broader health interventions		
Conception and pregnancy care	4,7%	3
Contraception	1,6%	1
Prevention, assessment and treatment of cervical cancer	3,1%	2
Safe abortion	4,7%	3
TB prevention, screening, diagnosis and treatment	6,3%	4
Screening and treatment for hazardous and harmful alcohol and other substance use	9,4%	6
<u>Mental health care</u>	62,5%	40

Table 5 provides detailed information about the challenges faced in the prevention, diagnosis, treatment, and care of communicable diseases among people who use drugs in the surveyed organisations' countries. This data, reflecting responses from various geographical, political and cultural contexts, underscores the multifaceted barriers that impede effective healthcare delivery. The insights drawn from this data not only highlight the predominant issues but also shed light on the societal and systemic changes needed to address these challenges comprehensively.

At the forefront of these challenges is the overwhelming impact of stigma and discrimination, with a staggering 78.1% of respondents identifying it as a critical barrier. This finding is not merely a statistic; it represents a deeply rooted societal issue that significantly hampers efforts towards effective healthcare for people who use drugs. Stigma, both societal and self-imposed, often leads to a reluctance to seek medical help for fear of judgment, discrimination, or even legal repercussions. This barrier is not just a reflection of societal attitudes but also points to a critical need for sensitisation and education among healthcare providers and the general public to foster a more inclusive and non-judgmental approach towards people who use drugs.

Mental health care is another significant area, with 62.5% of respondents recognising it as a major challenge under the broader health interventions. This indicates a recognition of the mental health needs of people who use drugs, aligning with global health perspectives that emphasise the integration of mental health care with drug-related services. The high percentage points to an urgent need for mental health services that are tailored to the complexities of substance use and its psychological impacts.

Punitive laws, policies, and practices were identified by 54.7% of respondents as another significant challenge. This insight underscores the complex interplay between legal frameworks and healthcare access. Punitive approaches to drug use prioritise criminalisation over healthcare, creating an environment where people who use drugs are more likely to avoid seeking help to evade legal consequences. This not only exacerbates the health and other risks associated with drug use and discriminatory policies but also places a considerable strain on the criminal justice system. The data calls for a paradigm shift towards more harm-reduction-focused policies that prioritise health and well-being over punitive measures.

Long-term housing, such as social housing and Housing First initiatives, is identified by 38% of respondents as a key challenge in the context of prevention, diagnosis, treatment and care of communicable diseases among people who use drugs in their country. Stable housing is fundamental to the well-being of people who use drugs, providing a secure environment that can facilitate access to health services and support networks. Housing First models, which do not require abstinence as a precondition, have shown success in improving housing stability and reducing substance use.

However, the availability of such housing remains limited, highlighting the need for expanded investment in long-term housing solutions. The data also highlights the challenges related to access to harm reduction interventions, with various interventions such as HAT, DCS and DCR, receiving 31.3%, 32.8%, and 34.4% respectively. These figures point to a significant gap in the availability and accessibility of these particular harm reduction services despite their proven effectiveness in minimising risks. This gap not only hinders the effective management of communicable diseases among people who use drugs but also reflects a broader issue of resource allocation and prioritisation within the drug policy and healthcare system.

Conclusions

The BOOST Project Multi-Modular Survey provides a comprehensive overview of the state of infectious diseases interventions within community-based harm reduction services across Europe, highlighting both achievements and ongoing challenges. The findings underscore the critical role these services play in addressing the health and social needs of people who use drugs, while also pointing to areas where further improvements are necessary.

Diversity and Availability of Services

The survey reveals a wide range of harm reduction services being offered, from core interventions like needle and syringe programs, opioid agonist treatment, and naloxone distribution, to more specialised services such as drug consumption rooms and drug checking. This diversity reflects a comprehensive approach to harm reduction, aimed at mitigating various risks associated with drug use. However, the uneven availability of certain services, such as heroin-assisted treatment, drug consumption rooms and drug checking, suggests that regulatory challenges, societal resistance, and resource constraints continue to limit the scope of harm reduction efforts.

Integration of Health Interventions

Community-based harm reduction services are crucial in providing access to health interventions related to infectious diseases. Services like infectious disease education, HIV testing, and condom distribution are widely available, indicating a strong integration of prevention and testing efforts within harm reduction settings. However, the limited availability of specialised interventions, such as pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) and post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) for HIV, highlights gaps in the continuum of care that need to be addressed to ensure comprehensive health support for people who use drugs.

Involvement of People with Lived and Living Experience

A significant strength of community-based harm reduction services is the involvement of people with lived or living experience of drug use.

This involvement enhances the relevance and effectiveness of services by incorporating first-hand insights and fostering trust within the community. However, the survey indicates that the involvement of these individuals in governance and monitoring and evaluation processes remains limited. Increasing their participation in these areas could lead to more inclusive and accountable decision-making within harm reduction organisations.

Barriers to Continuity of Care and Outreach

The survey highlights several barriers to ensuring continuity of care for individuals testing positive for infectious diseases. Stigma related to drug use and minority status is a major obstacle, affecting access to healthcare and perpetuating discrimination. Systemic barriers, such as limitations on treatment for individuals without health insurance and low accessibility of specialist services, further complicate the provision of comprehensive care. Addressing these barriers is essential to uphold principles of equity and non-discrimination in healthcare.

Outreach efforts to specific sub-populations of people who use drugs face significant challenges, including legal issues, limited capacity of services and staff, and a lack of meaningful involvement with these communities. These barriers highlight the need for targeted strategies and resource allocation to improve outreach and service provision to underserved groups, such as youth, individuals in prison settings, and migrants without legal rights to assistance.

The Role of Stigma

Across the data, stigma emerges as a pervasive and significant barrier in the area of harm reduction services, profoundly impacting the accessibility and effectiveness of interventions for people who use drugs. The survey data underscores that stigma related to drug use is a major obstacle, affecting both the willingness of individuals to seek help and the quality of care they receive. The reluctance to identify as a person who uses drugs due to fear of judgment or mistreatment leads to delayed diagnoses and treatment, exacerbating health disparities and contributing to the ongoing transmission of infectious diseases. Addressing stigma is therefore crucial not only for improving individual health outcomes but also for enhancing public health efforts.

Overall, the survey provides a comprehensive overview of the harm reduction landscape in Europe, highlighting both progress and areas for improvement. By addressing the identified challenges and implementing the recommended strategies, the harm reduction community can build on its successes and work towards a more comprehensive, equitable, and

inclusive approach to addressing the health and social needs of people who use drugs. This effort is essential for improving public health outcomes and ensuring that harm reduction services effectively support the well-being of this community.

Recommendations for Policy and Practice

Based on the survey findings, several key recommendations emerge for enhancing harm reduction efforts in Europe.

Expand Availability of Harm Reduction Interventions

Advocacy and policy reforms are needed to increase the availability of essential services, such as DCRs, drug checking, and HAT. This expansion requires addressing regulatory barriers and possible societal resistance.

Strengthen Integration with Healthcare Systems

Efforts should be made to integrate harm reduction services with broader healthcare systems, ensuring a seamless continuum of care from prevention and testing to treatment and long-term management of infectious diseases.

Combat Stigma and Discrimination

Reducing stigma and discrimination against people who use drugs is crucial for improving healthcare access and promoting inclusive environments. This requires public education and policy changes to foster acceptance and support.

Address Systemic Barriers

Policies should be reformed to eliminate barriers related to health insurance and treatment eligibility, ensuring that all individuals, regardless of their drug use status, can access necessary healthcare services.

Invest in Capacity Building

Increasing the capacity of harm reduction services through funding and resource allocation is essential to enhance outreach efforts and service provision, particularly for underserved populations.

Promote Involvement of People with Lived Experience

Encouraging the involvement of individuals with lived and living experience in all aspects of harm reduction service delivery, including governance and evaluation, can improve the effectiveness and accountability of these services.